

MECHANISM OF *s*-DIARYLTHIOCARBAMIDE FORMATION BY THE INTERACTION OF POTASSIUM ETHYL XANTHATE WITH AROMATIC PRIMARY AMINES

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•In the interaction of potassium ethyl xanthate (EtO.CS.SK) with aromatic primary amines (Ar.NH₂), leading to *s*-diarylthiocarbamides (ArNH.CS.NHAr), aryldithiocarbamates (ArNH.CS.SK) and arylthiourethanes (ArNH.CS.OEt) are the possible intermediate compounds. The interaction of these latter two compounds with aromatic primary amines and their pyrolytic behaviour under analogous conditions have been studied. A mechanism has been suggested for the xanthate-amine reaction under consideration where aromatic thiourethanes appear to be the probable intermediates. The investigation incidentally throws light also on the formation of *s*-diarylthiocarbamides from aromatic dithiocarbamates and thiourethanes.

Direct interaction of aromatic primary amines and potassium ethyl xanthate at 140-80° leads to almost exclusive formation of *s*-diarylthiocarbamides (Sahasrabudhey, Nambury and Bhraramamba, *Proc. Ind. Sci. Cong.*, 1958, Part III, p. 145). The reaction was tentatively represented as

But since two functional groups of xanthate, viz., -OEt and -SK, were replaced by arylamino residues, probably the reaction took place in more than one stages, and either ArNH.CS.OEt (arylthiourethane) or ArNH.CS.SK (aryldithiocarbamate) or both of these were intermediate products. In the interaction of carbon disulphide and aromatic amines in presence of alcoholic alkali at 100°, thiourethanes are known to be formed (Losanitsch, *Ber.*, 1882, 15, 470; 1883, 16, 49; Fry, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 25, 1539) and the intermediate role of dithiocarbamates (Snedker, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1925, 44, 741) leading either to mustard oils (Fromm, *Annalen*, 1906, 348, 144) or to thiuramdisulphides (Braun, *Ber.*, 1900, 33, 2726; 1906, 39, 4369) prior to thiocarbamide formation is beyond doubt. Further, amine-dithiocarbamates have also been reported to furnish *s*-disubstituted thiocarbamides by direct pyrolysis (Connor in Gilman's Organic Chemistry, 2nd ed., 1949, Vol. I, p. 941; Losanitsch, *Ber.*, 1891, 24, 302a).

The present investigation was carried out in order to throw light on the mechanism of primary aromatic amine-xanthate reaction, referred to above (*loc. cit.*).

Interaction of phenyl- and *p*-tolyl-thiourethanes and dithiocarbamates with aniline and other aromatic primary amines was studied under the relevant conditions. A pyrolytic study of phenyl- and *p*-tolyl-thiourethanes and ammonium salts of respective dithiocarbamic acids was also carried out. The results are presented in the Experimental part and in Tables I and II and their implications have been discussed (*vide infra*).

It is concluded that an aryldithiocarbamate is not involved at any stage in this change. The reaction proceeds, most probably, through a thiourethane, the -OEt group of which is replaced with -NHAr, forming *s*-diarylthiocarbamide (*vide infra*). Under the conditions of experiments reported, there is very little possibility of the thiourethane dissociating into alcohol and mustard oil and the latter combining with excess of amine to afford thiocarbamide (*vide Discussion*). The principal changes taking place may be represented as follows :

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Phenyl- and *p*-tolyl-thiourethanes were obtained by the action of aniline and *p*-toluidine on EtO.CS.S.S.CS.OEt (diethyl disulphur dicarbothionate; Hofmann, *Ber.*, 1870, 3, 774; Liebermann, *Annalen*, 1881, 207, 121).

Ammonium salts of phenyl-, *o*-tolyl- and *p*-tolyl-dithiocarbamic acids were obtained by the usual method (Vogel, "Practical Organic Chemistry", 1954, p. 615).

Action of Aniline, o-Toluidine and p-Toluidine with the respective Dithiocarbamates: Isolation of s-Diarylthiocarbamides.—Required quantities of the dithiocarbamate and the respective amine were mixed (in some cases alcoholic medium was employed) and maintained at the desired temperature (30-180°) for the required duration of time. At higher temperatures vigorous reaction commenced immediately with the evolution of gases in which smell of ammonia and carbon disulphide was perceptible. In the experiments where alcohol was present, a red deposit of ammonium dithiocarbamate (identified through its *s*-benzylisothiuronium derivative, m.p. 66-68°) was obtained on the condenser walls. The reaction mixture was treated with HCl (dil.) to remove the unchanged amine and the dithiocarbamate and the solid residue of the *s*-diarylthiocarbamide collected, weighed and identified. The results are presented in Table I.

Pyrolytic Decomposition of Ammonium-Phenyldithiocarbamate.—Ammonium phenyldithiocarbamate (5 g.) was heated at its melting point (110°) for 1 hour. Smell of carbon disulphide and ammonia was perceptible. The product on treatment with dilute hydrochloric acid gave a small quantity (0.215 g., 7%) of thiocarbamide. The filtrate on evaporation gave 1.20 g. of aniline hydrochloride.

TABLE I

*Interaction of aniline, o-toluidine and p-toluidine with dithiocarbamates**

No.	Dithiocarbamate (ammonium salts)	Amine.	Heating Temp.	Duration.	M.P. (crude product)	Crude yield of NN'-diarylthiocarbamide for n.ed.	% Yield.
1	Amm. phenyl-	Aniline.				Thiocarbamilide**.	
	3.7 g.	3.7 c.c.	30-40°	48 hr.	146-48°	0.70 g.	15
2	5.6	5.6	90-95°	2	134-40°	1.27	*†18.5
3a	5.6+15 c.c. alcohol	5.6	"	1	145-50°	2.30	‡34
3b	Do	5.6	"	1	145-47°	2.60	38
4	3.7 g.	3.7	120-25°	1	135-40°	0.60	13
5	3.7	3.7	140°	1	145-48°	0.36	8
6	3.7	1.8	"	1½	146-48°	0.27	6
7	3.7	0.9	"	1	144-47°	0.24	11
8	3.7	5.6	180°	1	145-47°	0.55	12
9	3.7	3.7	"	1	146-48°	0.46	10
10	3.7	1.8	"	1	144-47°	0.40	9
11	5.0	Nil	100-110°	1	150-52°	0.215	‡7
12	Amm. o-tolyl-	o-Toluidine.				s-Di-o-tolylthiocarbamide**	
	5.3 g. +15 c.c. alcohol	5.5 c.c.	90-95°	1	160-65°	1.2	†18
13	4.0	4.0	140°	1	156-57°	0.5	10
14	4.0	6.0	180°	1	160-61°	0.64	14
15	4.2	4.2	"	1	160-61°	0.25	5
16	4.0	2.0	"	1	159-61°	0.65	11
17	Amm. p-tolyl-	p-Toluidine.				s-Di-p-tolylthiocarbamide**.	
	5.2+15 c.c. alcohol	5.2 g.	90-95°	1	179-81°	2.42	†36
18	4.0	4.0	140°	1	169-70°	1.04	25
19	4.0	6.0	180°	1	180-81°	1.85	36
20	4.0	4.0	100°	1	178-80°	1.74	34
21	4.0	2.0	"	1	172-74°	2.50	52

* NH₂ and CS₂ were identified in all cases and ammonium dithiocarbamate isolated and identified in some cases (vide Experimental).

** Identified through undepressed m.p. of the mixture with authentic samples.

*† A small trace of phenylthiourea was identified.

† The conditions in these experiments correspond more with those usually applied for the preparation of thiocarbamilide from CS₂ and aniline than with xanthate-amine reaction reported earlier.

‡ Pyrolytic decomposition (vide Experimental).

Action of Aniline, p- and o-Toluidines with Phenyl and p-Tolyl-thiourelhanes: Formation of sym. and mixed Diarylthiocarbamides.—Required quantities of amine and thiourelthane, were heated under reflux at 180° (or lower temperatures) for the desired duration of time. To remove the unchanged amine and the thiourelthane, the product was first treated with HCl (dil.) and then with a cold 6% NaOH solution. The residue left proved to be the related diarylthiocarbamide. The results along with relevant data have been summarised in Table II.

TABLE II
Interaction of aniline, o-toluidine and p-toluidine with phenyl- and p-tolyl-thiourethanes.

No.	Thiourethane.	Amlue.	Heating Temp.	Duration.	Crude yield of thiocarbamide.	% Yield.	Cryat. from.	*Product.	M.P.
1.	Phenyl- (2 g.)	Aniline (2 c.c.)	180°	1 hr.	1.5 g.	60	Alcohol	Thiocarbaniide	150-52°
2.	p-Tolyl- (2 g.)	p-Toluidine (2 g.)	"	1	2.1	80	Chlorobenzene	s-Di-p-tolylthiourea	181°
3.	p-Tolyl- (2 g.)	Aniline (1 c.c.)	100°	1	Nil	...	...	...	...
	"	"	120°	1	"	...	...	...	...
	"	"	140°	1	"	...	...	...	...
	"	(2 c.c.)	180°	1	1.4	52	90% EtOH	N-Phenyl-N'-p-tolylthiourea	147-49°
	"	"	"	"	"	"	"	"	"
4.	Phenyl- (2 g.)	o-Toluidine (2 c.c.)	180°	1	1.9	72	"	N'-phenyl-N'-o-tolylthiourea	149-50°
5.	(1.8 g.)	(1 c.c.)	120°	1	Traces	...	Alcohol	Thiocarbaniide**	152-53°
6.	(2 g.)	(2 c.c.)	140°	5 mins.	0.13 g.	5	"	N'-Phenyl-N'-o-tolylthiourea	149-50°
	"	"	180°	"	0.8	30	"	"	"
	"	"	"	10 "	1.2	45	"	"	"
	"	"	"	15 "	1.4	52	"	"	"
	"	"	"	2 hrs.	1.9	71	"	"	"

* In all cases authenticity of the product was confirmed by melting point of its mixture with genuine samples.

** Trace of thiocarbaniide formed may be due to the pyrolytic decomposition of phenylthiourethane.

Pyrolytic Decomposition of p-Tolyl- and Phenyl-thiourethanes.—*p*-Tolylthiourethane (4 g.) was heated under reflux at 180° for 1 hour and the product treated with HCl (dil.) and alkali as above. The solid left behind (0.4 g.) proved to be *s*-di-*p*-tolylthiourea. The acidic filtrate was extracted with benzene and the benzene extract was mixed with a little aniline and left overnight. From this on evaporation *N*-phenyl-*N'*-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide (0.11 g., m.p. 142-43°) was obtained. This indicates formation of *p*-tolyl isothiocyanate in traces only.

From phenylthiourethane (2 g.), decomposed in an analogous manner, 0.25 g. of thiocarbamilide and a small quantity of phenylisothiocyanate, identified through *N*-phenyl-*N'*-*o*-tolylthiocarbamide (m.p. 142-143°), were obtained.

In another experiment, phenylthiourethane (5 g.) was heated at 180° for 1 hour as in the above case, and the mass was steam-distilled for 3 hours. Smell of mustard oil was perceptible in the distillate and crystals were observed in the distillate as well as on the sides of the condenser. The distillate was extracted out with ether and the ether evaporated. The residue was treated overnight with strong aqueous ammonia and all the solid was collected and washed with ether (to remove phenylthiourethane which does not react with ammonia) when a trace (less than 0.1 g.) of phenylthiourea was left behind. The ethereal washings gave 1.1 g. of phenylthiourethane more of which was recovered from the distillation flask (2.1 g.). Thus even after one hour's heating at 180°, major part of the thiourethane remained unchanged. Only traces of mustard oil were formed.

Pyrolysis of Phenylthiourethane at its boiling point.—Phenylthiourethane (3.2 g.) was heated under reflux at its b.p. (211-13°) for 1 hour and the product steam-distilled (3 hours). No crystals were formed in this case in the condenser or the distillate. The latter was extracted out with ether, which on evaporation gave about 0.70 c.c. of an oil. On treatment with aniline in benzene, the oil gave 0.6 g. of thiocarbamilide, thus proving its identity with phenyl isothiocyanate. The yield of mustard oil in this experiment corresponded with nearly 25%. From the distillation flask nearly 0.7 g. of a brown resinous solid (m.p. 65-68°) was collected, which was insoluble in dilute sodium hydroxide and therefore it was not thiourethane.

Isolation of p-Tolylthiourethane from p-Toluidine—Xanthate Reaction.—In the experiments reported (*loc. cit.*) at 140-80° with reactants, one or the other in small excess, no thiourethane could be isolated in the products. In view of its great capacity to react with amines, the following experiment with a very large excess of xanthate was undertaken.

p-Toluidine (2.3 g.) and a large excess of potassium ethyl xanthate (6.4 g.) were mixed and heated at 180° for 2 hours. The product was treated with water and HCl (dil.), and the solid residue extracted with alcohol. On evaporation of the alcoholic extract and cooling, a solid was obtained, which on repeated extraction with cold 6% NaOH solution and neutralisation of the alkali, gave 0.15 g. of *p*-tolylthiourethane, m.p. 83-84° (mixed m.p. with an authentic sample).

The alkali-insoluble part of the residue from alcohol consisted mainly of *s*-di-*p*-tolylthiourea; it contained traces of a higher melting solid (m.p. 236°), identified with *s*-di-*p*-tolylurea,

DISCUSSION

The direct interaction of aniline, *o*-toluidine and *p*-toluidine with the respective ammonium aryldithiocarbamates gave 6-18.5%, 5-14% and 25-52% of the corresponding *NN'*-diarylthiocarbamides (vide Table I). The same reactants in presence of alcohol gave better yields of thiocarbamides, viz., 38%, 18% and 36% respectively (Table I, Expts. 3, 12 and 17). But in an alcoholic medium, the conditions corresponded more with those usually applied for the preparation of thiocarbamilide from carbon disulphide and aniline, than those employed in the xanthate—amine reaction under discussion. Further, there is no material difference in the yields of thiocarbamides at different temperatures, which is contrary to the observed higher yields at 180° than at 140°, and almost imperceptible reaction at 100° in the case of the direct interaction of these amines with potassium ethyl xanthate (Sahasrabudhey *et al.*, *loc. cit.*).

The pyrolysis of ammonium phenyldithiocarbamate (5 g.) at 110° (vide Experimental and Table I, Expt. 11) gave only 7% thiocarbamilide (0.215 g.) and very considerable quantities of free aniline (isolated as hydrochloride, 1.23 g.), ammonia and CS₂. This quantity of thiocarbamilide is of the same order as obtained in above experiments which suggests that in both cases it most probably arises from the dithiocarbamate by identical reactions, irrespective of the external presence or absence of the amine. The products of pyrolysis, in fact, indicate dissociation of the major part of the dithiocarbamate into amine, ammonia and CS₂. The thiocarbamilide formed is a secondary product and is not produced directly from the dithiocarbamate as in the case of aliphatic compounds (Hofmann, *Ber.*, 1868, 1, 25).

In the light of these facts, formation of a dithiocarbamate as an intermediate product in the xanthate-amine reaction appears unlikely. Moreover, a dithiocarbamate has also not been detected in the products.

Aniline and *p*-toluidine reacted at 180° with phenyl- and *p*-tolyl-thiourethanes, giving rise to the corresponding *NN'*-diarylthiocarbamides in 60% and 80% yields (Table II, Expts. 1 and 2). *N*-phenyl-*N'*-*p*-tolyl- and- *o*-tolyl-thiocarbamides were also obtained in good yields (52 and 72% respectively), by the interaction of aniline with *p*-tolylthiourethane and *o*-toluidine with phenylthiourethane respectively (Table II Expts. 3 and 4). These yields accord well with those obtained by the direct interaction of these amines with potassium ethyl xanthate (*loc. cit.*).

The interaction of thiourethane and amine takes place readily at 180°; at lower temperatures the reaction is slower (vide Table II), which is in agreement with the reported higher yields at 180° than at 140°, and the almost imperceptible reaction at 100°, observed in the direct amine—xanthate reaction.

Pyrolysis of phenyl- and *p*-tolyl-thiourethanes at 180° (vide Experimental) gave very small quantities of the corresponding diarylthiocarbamides and traces only of mustard oil. At the boiling point (211-13°) of phenylthiourethane, mustard oil formation was considerable (vide Experimental; also Hofmann, *Ber.*, 1869, 2, 120; 1870, 3, 772), but at lower temperatures, viz., 140-80°, which have been operative

in the xanthate-amine experiments reported, the possibility of mustard oil playing the role of an intermediate compound is indeed very limited. Dyson and Browne (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 3285; Gilman, "Organic Chemistry", 2nd ed., pp. 1058-59) report the reaction,

to be irreversible at about 80° and the present experiments (*vide supra*) indicate more or less the same thing at 180°. In the light of these facts, it is more than probable that under the conditions of experiments reported earlier (140-80°), the -OEt group of thiourethane is directly replaced by ArNH- group.

The formation of thiourethanes, as the first stage in the xanthate-amine reaction, is supported by the isolation of small quantities of *p*-tolylthiourethane, when a large excess of xanthate was used (*vide Experimental*). Moreover, it is known that -SK is less firmly held as compared to -OEt in the xanthate and also in the *o*-ethyl ester of monothiocarbonic acid (EtO.CO.SK) and, hence, it is likely to be replaced more easily by an arylamino group. Thus:

The intermediate formation of thiourethanes is also supported by analogy with aliphatic thiourethanes, which are formed in almost quantitative yields by direct interaction of aliphatic amines with xanthate (Nambury, *J. Vsk. Univ.*, 1958, 2, No. 1, p. 101).

That thiourethanes cannot be isolated in most cases in the xanthate-aromatic amine reaction would appear to be the main objection to their role as intermediates in the formation of *s* diarylthiocarbamides. But this is probably explained by the fact that the temperature range at which their formation takes place (above 120°) coincides with temperatures at which they react with amines (140-80°) and that this latter reaction is very fast (*vide Table II, Expt. 6, also Degering, "Organic Nitrogen Compounds", 1945, p. 456*).

In the light of the above facts, the following sequence of changes is indicated in the xanthate-amine reaction:

and to a small extent at 180° (but more probable at higher temperatures).

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